

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
California State University, Long Beach
California State University, Los Angeles

PRACTICE GUIDELINES FOR LABOR
EPIDURAL ADMINISTRATION

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Labor epidurals are the most widely used form of analgesia for laboring patients, as they provide the most effective pain relief as compared to other methods. When unsuccessful, labor epidurals are deemed “failures” and provide inadequate labor analgesia, decrease patient satisfaction, and can pose a life-threatening risk in the surgical suite by requiring additional anesthetic. A 4-month audit of medical records found an 8.2% failure rate among epidurals (46/559) at a local southern California hospital. Results of an extensive literature review uncovered many factors that can lead to improved patient analgesia with epidural use as well as decrease epidural failure rates. Evidence-based recommendations for epidural placement to decrease lack of analgesia include combined spinal/epidural technique or dural puncture epidural technique to confirm proximity of the epidural space, use of ultrasound in patients with difficult anatomy, and securing the catheter with patients relaxed or in the lateral position to avoid having the catheter pulled out. One-sided blocks can be decreased with the bevel of the epidural needle facing cephalad and leaving 5 cm or less of the catheter in the epidural space. In order to prevent failed surgical anesthesia, it is recommended that an epidural catheter be replaced if multiple boluses are needed to maintain patient comfort. Additionally, programmed intermittent epidural bolus technique may provide superior analgesia, decreasing the need for intervention. Finally, loss of resistance to saline is recommended to avoid a pneumocephalus. An implementation/evaluation plan for these recommendations was developed.

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BACKGROUND

A comfortable labor experience is the driving force for patient satisfaction in the obstetric setting. Epidurals offer optimal analgesia as compared to other available pain management options during labor (Muppuri, Gupta, Agarwal, & Soskin, 2012). Inadequate analgesia from labor epidurals decreases patient satisfaction and poses a life-threatening risk in the surgical suite when cesarean section is performed. There is currently a wide discrepancy regarding the rate of failed epidurals reported (0.9% -24%); however, many studies have found best practice techniques can minimize the rate (Agaram, Douglas, McTaggart, & Gunka, 2007).

Epidural Failures: Definitions and Rates

Continuous labor epidurals (CLE) are the most widely used form of analgesia for women in labor as they provide the most effective pain relief compared to other methods (Muppuri et al., 2012). On a national level, epidural use for labor analgesia has been reported as high as 70% (Guglielminotti, Mentre, Bedairia, Montravers, & Longrois, 2013). Epidurals work by injecting a concentration of local anesthetic through a catheter placed in the epidural space (Simmons, Taghizadeh, Dennis, Hughes, & Cyna, 2012). They can be administered either by a continuous infusion at a rate set by the provider or by patient self-management, also known as patient-controlled epidural analgesia (PCEA; Simmons et al., 2012). Both methods allow analgesia to last throughout labor.

Reports of failures in labor epidural analgesia range from 0.9% to 24% (Agaram et al., 2007). Failures occur when any of the following occur: a one-sided block, a “patchy” block, a block requiring multiple top-off doses of local anesthetic, and lack of analgesia requiring replacement of the epidural catheter. The most common explanations

for inadequate analgesia with epidurals include wrong location of catheter, migration of catheter, compartmentalization within tissue, blockage, or disconnection (Muppuri et al., 2012). The end result, unfortunately, is inadequate analgesia, a poor labor experience, and decreased patient satisfaction.

Epidural failures are sometimes associated with cesarean section deliveries. With epidurals as the most common form of labor analgesia, patients often present to the operating room for cesarean section with an epidural in place following a trial of labor (Carvalho, 2012). In this situation, the inability to use an epidural for surgical anesthesia significantly increases the risk of maternal morbidity associated with obstetrical anesthesia. Problems include airway emergencies, aspiration, awareness under anesthesia, depressant effects on the fetus and tone of the uterus, and difficult postoperative pain management (Bauer, Kountanis, Tsen, Greenfield, & Mhyre, 2012). There is also a significant increase in cost for the hospital when general anesthesia needs to be implemented after a failure in neuraxial anesthesia. This problem has become so substantial that the Royal College of Anaesthetists has produced guidelines for a suitable rate of failed regional anesthesia for cesarean sections (Carvalho, 2012). In these guidelines, necessity of conversion to general anesthesia for cesarean sections should typically be < 1% for non-emergent and < 3% for emergent cesarean sections (Carvalho, 2012). Currently, in the United States, the failure rate for epidural use in cesarean sections is 7.1%, almost double the British recommendation and there are no current national guidelines (Pan, Bogard, & Owen, 2004).

Needs Assessment

Techniques for placing labor epidurals vary from provider to provider and many studies show factors that contribute to a higher risk of epidural failure rate. My current facility has 29 Certified Registered Nurse Anesthetists (CRNAs) and 11 Medical Doctors of Anesthesia (MDAs) who provide labor analgesia on an obstetric rotation. Individual providers have developed their own ways of placing epidural catheters based on their level of comfort. However, no evidence-based guideline exists regarding techniques in placing labor epidurals in order to decrease the risk of inadequate analgesia. The purpose of my Doctor of Nursing Practice project is to develop a practice guideline for obstetric anesthesia providers that will optimize analgesia in labor epidurals.

Supporting Framework

As seen in Figure 1, the supporting theoretical framework chosen for this project is the Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care (Titler, Stelman, Budreau, Buckwalter, & Goode, 2001). Appropriately chosen evidence is used to guide improvements in the practice setting and provide a base for improved practice guidelines (Polit & Beck, 2012). New practice guidelines are developed to improve care and increase patient satisfaction.

Problem Focused Triggers

A problem-focused trigger refers to a problem in the practice setting that requires a solution (Polit & Beck, 2012). The focus of this project is to address failed labor epidural rates. Failed epidurals have many detrimental side effects that include decreased patient satisfaction, a poor labor experience, and increased mortality rates in the operative suite. This problem has become clinically significant, as the patient satisfaction rates in

The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care

◇ = a decision point

Titler, M.G., C., Steelman, V.J., Rakel, B. A., Budreau, G., Everett, L.Q., Buckwaller, K.C., Tripp-Reimer, T., & Goode C. (2001). The Iowa Model Of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care. *Critical Care Nursing Clinics of North America*, 13(4), 497-509.

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Figure 1. The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care.

my work setting are low regarding laboring experiences, and this low satisfaction may result from epidural failures, although the exact rate of failure is unknown. The goal of this project is to help increase patient analgesia during labor, and therefore provide a better experience for laboring women.

Form a Team

In order to be successful in implementing the new practice guideline, it is important to have a team of influential providers promoting the change (Titler et al., 2001). Since this has already been addressed as a quality improvement issue in my organization, getting buy-in from stakeholders should be relatively easy. The team of providers necessary for the implementation of this guideline will include the Chief of Anesthesiology, the Department Administrator, Chief of Obstetrics/Gynecology, labor and delivery nurse manager, and CRNAs and MDAs who provide labor anesthesia. Their expertise and level of authority will be helpful in implementing this change.

Assemble, Critique, and Synthesize Literature

This part of the project entailed finding and disseminating the research/evidence that was used to develop the practice guideline (Titler et al., 2001). A thorough review of the literature was performed and randomized control trials (RCTs), meta-analyses, and systematic reviews were sought out. This literature was then thoroughly studied for applicability, merit, and clinical relevance (Titler et al., 2001). Once all of the literature was reviewed, it was then synthesized to ensure enough research was available to guide practice and implement guidelines (Titler et al., 2001).

Pilot the Change in Practice

Before the guideline is implemented into practice, it needs to be piloted in order to determine the ease and effectiveness of the proposed guideline (Titler et al., 2001). Having achievable outcomes and baseline data, a developed and implementation plan, and then, evaluating and modifying as necessary are important components of this step (Titler et al., 2001).

Institute the Change in Practice

After the pilot test is complete, the next step is to review the outcomes and adopt the new practice if change is deemed appropriate (Titler et al., 2001). If the outcomes of the pilot study are unfavorable, then the process needs to be re-evaluated with further research implemented. If there continues to be a problem with quality improvement, yet no new research is available, expert opinion or theory may be adopted and implemented.

Monitor and Analyze Structure, Process, and Outcome Data

The final phase of the Iowa Model deals with outcome evaluation (Titler et al., 2001). For this particular project, as the new recommendations are being implemented, patient satisfaction with analgesia should be monitored along with rates of epidural failure, and provider understanding about the recommendations will need to be evaluated along with problems in implementation. The goal is that providers will have a better understanding of factors that will decrease failure rates in epidurals, will change their practice to match recommendations, and better analgesia will result for laboring women. This in turn will cause increased patient satisfaction. Finally, it is imperative that the results of this evaluation be shared with others in order to promote the adoption of this guideline in other facilities (Titler et al., 2001).

Purpose Statement and Objectives

The purpose of this project is to develop a practice guideline for epidural placement and management that will increase patient analgesia and satisfaction in the obstetric setting and to implement this in my work setting as a best practice technique. A major goal of this project will be to improve epidural placement techniques by nurse anesthetists and therefore, to decrease the failure rate of labor epidurals. In order to detect changes in failure rates, the failure rate for labor epidurals will be assessed for a 4-month period before and after implementation of the guideline to determine effectiveness. Following the development of a local practice guideline and if time permits, anesthesia providers will be educated on the best practice techniques for increasing epidural effectiveness and labor and delivery patients will have better labor analgesia. The current failure rate for labor epidurals will be assessed before the implementation of the guideline and reassessed after implementation to determine effectiveness. A decrease in overall epidural failure rates will indicate successful implementation and validate the importance of this project.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

The primary objective for this project was to conduct an extensive literature review regarding best practice techniques for labor epidural administration. A total of 44 articles were utilized in this project and have been incorporated into eight tables of evidence based on the appropriate labor epidural technique. The techniques included combined spinal epidural technique/dural puncture epidural technique, needle placement/depth of catheter, dosing regimen/opioid administration, loss of resistance technique, multiport/uniport catheters, patient positioning, pre-distention of the epidural space, and predictors of difficult epidural placement.

The secondary objective for this project was to review current local hospital labor and delivery statistics for failed epidural rates. A total of 559 labor epidural placements were analyzed during a 4-month period. The final objective for this project was to develop practice guidelines to support anesthesia providers administering obstetric anesthesia.

Prevalence of Epidural Failures

While epidurals remain the most successful pain relief method for laboring women, many factors contribute to inadequate analgesia. Some risk factors associated with failed epidurals include patient history of scoliosis, morbid obesity, and a previous failed labor epidural. The large discrepancy in overall failure rates of labor epidurals can be attributed to the lack of a formal definition of a true epidural failure (Thangamuthu, Russell, & Purva, 2013). Current literature reports that epidural failure rates are 0.9% - 24% (Agaram et al., 2007; Thangamuthu et al., 2013). Labor epidural failures for this project included those with reported absence of analgesia, one-sided analgesia,

inadvertent intravascular puncture, and inability to convert to surgical anesthesia. These same criteria were used to assess rates of failed epidurals before and after implementation of the practice guidelines in order to ensure consistency and adequacy of data.

Combined Spinal/Epidural and Dural Puncture

A multitude of techniques are available for anesthesiologists in providing labor analgesia and include administration of intravenous opioids, traditional labor epidural, combined spinal/epidural (CSE), and dural puncture epidural (DPE) technique. A traditional labor epidural refers to local anesthetic that is administered into the epidural space only. A CSE is a technique where after location of the epidural space, a spinal needle is threaded into the epidural needle and punctures the subarachnoid space. Local anesthetic is then injected into the subarachnoid space and the needle is removed and additional local anesthetic is placed into the epidural space. The advantage of this is a quicker onset of analgesia. DPE is a relatively newer technique that is very similar to the CSE technique except that medication is not placed into the subarachnoid space once it is punctured. The rationale for this technique is that just by creating a puncture, some medication that is placed into the epidural space will be passively transferred into the subarachnoid space (Cappiello, O'Rourke, Segal, & Tsen, 2008).

Five studies were analyzed to compare the analgesic effects of each of these techniques. Cappiello et al. (2008) performed a randomized control trial that looked at the analgesic effect of DPE technique versus traditional labor epidural technique. The results showed that DPE technique patients had faster sacral dermatome analgesia and lower pain scores. Two studies compared the analgesic effects of CSE versus traditional labor epidurals. The study performed by Gambling, Berkowitz, Farrell, Pue, and Shay

(2013) was a randomized controlled trial, and the study performed by Heesen et al. (2013) was a meta-analysis comparing 10 studies. In conclusion, both sets of authors favor the CSE technique over the traditional labor epidural technique finding that the CSE provided quicker onset and better first stage analgesia as well as fewer one-sided blocks.

Epidural Needle Bevel Orientation and Depth of Catheter

Bevel rotation and depth of epidural catheter can affect the spread of medications that are injected in the epidural space. The bevel of the epidural needle is typically placed either laterally or horizontally into the patients back. Huffnagle et al. (1998) performed a randomized control study looking at four different bevel rotations on spread of local anesthetic. These authors also looked at the effect of rotating the bevel on dural puncture rates, as this had been a long-standing concern. They concluded that entering the epidural space with a lateral facing bevel and rotating 90 degrees once in the epidural space provided patients with a high level of symmetrical blocks and improved analgesia. No dural punctures resulted from this technique showing that it is both a safe and effective technique.

Catheter depth is determined by how much catheter is left in the epidural space and is provider specific. The depth of the catheter in the epidural space is measured by subtracting the depth at which loss of resistance was found from the depth of catheter insertion. For example, if loss of resistance is measured at 5 cm and the catheter is measuring 12 cm at the skin, then 7 cm of catheter is left inside the epidural space. Two studies have evaluated the effect of catheter depth on anesthetic outcome. Beilin, Bernstein, and Zucker-Pinchoff (2000) compared three catheter depths (3, 5, and 7 cm)

on labor analgesia and complications. They found that catheters threaded 5 cm resulted in the highest success of analgesia and had fewer complications as compared to the 7 cm group. In a systematic review with a similar research question, Mhyre, Greenfield, Tsen, and Polley (2009) looked at the effect of catheter depth of intravenous cannulation. Two randomized control trials were included in this study and documented that limiting the catheter depth to less than 6 cm significantly reduced the risk of venous cannulation.

Epidural Opioids/Dosing Regimen

Dosing of an epidural catheter can be done many ways including a continuous infusion, intermittent programmed boluses, or a combination of the two. George, Allen, and Habib (2013) performed a systematic review and meta-analysis in order to compare the intermittent bolus regimen with the traditional epidural regimen. The results showed that intermittent bolus epidurals decreased the total amount of local anesthetic, improved patient satisfaction, and decreased anesthetic interventions. Subsequent studies supported this finding that epidural bolus resulted in less bupivacaine consumption and increased patient satisfaction (Wong, McCarthy, & Hewlett, 2011; Wong et al., 2006). In the 2011 study, Wong et al. (2011) looked at specific time intervals and volumes of local anesthetic delivered and found that a 10 ml bolus every 60 minutes provided the best patient analgesia.

Epidural opioids are frequently mixed with local anesthetic for an additional analgesic effect. Ginosar and colleagues (2003) looked at the mode of action of fentanyl when delivered intravenously and epidurally. The results showed that when fentanyl is co-administered with local anesthetic, it is 3 times as potent as intravenously administered fentanyl and therefore is presumed to have a spinal mechanism of action.

Halpern et al. (2004) compared the analgesic effect of fentanyl administered intravenously versus epidurally. Patients who received epidural fentanyl had a much higher satisfaction with their analgesia and less nausea, drowsiness, and need for neonatal resuscitation. Finally, Capogna, Camorcia, Stirparo, and Farcomeni (2003) compared the potency of fentanyl and sufentanil administered in the epidural space and found minimum effective analgesic doses to be 124.2 mcg and 21.1 mcg, respectively. This gives providers a benchmark for clinical use when co-administering opioids with local anesthetic.

Epidural Space Identifier

The epidural space is typically found with one of two techniques: loss of resistance to air or fluid. Both techniques are effective ways of locating the epidural space; however, it is imperative for providers to be aware of the risks associated with each technique. Muppuri et al. (2012) performed an observation study on 502 laboring women and found that air had a significantly higher rate of inadequate epidural anesthesia when compared to saline. Segal and Arendt (2010) found no difference in regards to anesthetic outcomes when comparing air to saline; however more attempts were needed to find the epidural space when using air. In a meta-analysis, Schier et al. (2009) found no difference in complications when comparing loss of resistance of air to saline. While both techniques seem to be equal in effectiveness, saline presents a slight advantage over air due to some contraindications to using air. If a dural puncture has occurred and the provider needs to access a different level, air should not be used for loss of resistance as some air can be inadvertently transferred into the subarachnoid space

causing a pneumocephalus. The same theory holds true when administering an epidural blood patch in which saline is the recommended loss of resistance technique.

Multiport/Uniport Catheters

There are two types of epidural catheters for delivery of local anesthetic: uniport catheters and multiport catheters. In a randomized control trial, D'Angelo, Foss, and Livesay (1997) compared the use of multiport versus uniport catheters on epidural insertion-related complications. Researchers found that multiport catheters resulted in better analgesia and fewer manipulations by anesthesia providers. In a systematic review, Mhyre et al. (2009) included five studies evaluating the effect of different catheters on intravascular cannulation. They concluded that uniport catheters have lower rates of intravascular cannulation as compared to multiport catheters.

Patient Positioning

Patients receiving labor epidurals are either positioned sitting up or lying on their hip. The comfort level of the provider administering the epidural is often the determinant of patient position in epidural placement. However, there are times when a patient is unable to sit up for an epidural necessitating the lateral position. This may occur when the patient is almost completely dilated, or is experiencing too much pain to remain still in the seated position. Bahar et al. (2004) looked at the effect of patient positioning on inadvertent intravenous cannulation and found that the lateral position significantly decreased the occurrence of vessel catheterization. This is probably due to the reduction of venous engorgement in the epidural space when lying versus sitting. Mhyre et al. (2009) found evidence supporting this in a systematic review comparing six trials. The

occurrence of vessel cannulation was 11.9% and 6.7% with sitting versus lateral position respectively.

Saline Pre-distention of Epidural Space

Once the epidural space is located, saline is often administered through the epidural needle in order to distend the epidural space. This pre-distention with fluid helps to push vessels out of the way and make a clear path for easy and atraumatic catheter insertion. In separate randomized trials, Evron et al. (2007) and Gadalla et al. (2003) found that pre-distention with 5-10 ml of fluid prior to epidural catheter insertion significantly reduced the risk of venous cannulation. A systematic review performed by Mhyre et al. (2009) further strengthened these findings; eight randomized control trials showed a decrease in intravascular cannulation with fluid pre-distention.

Predictors of Epidural Failures

Patients often present to labor and delivery units with pre-existing risk factors for inadequate labor analgesia. Obstetric anesthesia providers must be cognizant of these risk factors in order to decrease the risk of a failed epidural and poor maternal satisfaction. A large risk to the obstetric patient, which increases maternal morbidity and mortality, is having a failed epidural when needed for a cesarean section and the need to perform general anesthesia on these patients. Following a systematic review to evaluate risks associated with the inability to use epidural for surgical anesthesia, Bauer et al. (2012) found that an increase in number of boluses needed during labor was correlated with failed surgical epidural anesthesia. In a retrospective chart review, Riley and Papasin (2001) also found that the increase in top off doses was directly related to poor

surgical anesthesia. In obstetric cases where these factors are present, it is recommended that the epidural catheter be replaced if surgical intervention seems likely in order to spare the patient of general anesthesia or from receiving a total spinal block.

Guglielminotti et al. (2013) looked at certain traits that increase the likelihood of inadequate analgesia. The significant findings of this report included the inability to palpate the spinous processes, the inability of the patient to bend over, and a spinal deformity. Patients who present with these risk factors may benefit from interventions such as ultrasound in order to facilitate placement. Vallejo, Phelps, Singh, Orebaugh, and Sah (2010) performed a randomized control trial to look at the effect of ultrasound on number of epidural replacements. Their results showed a significant decrease in trials of epidural placement as well as the amount of catheter replacements with ultrasound use.

METHODS

The methods used in this project focused on developing anesthesia practice guidelines for obstetrical anesthesia providers who administer labor epidurals. Collecting data on failure rates before and after guideline implementation required local hospital as well as university Institutional Review Board (IRB) approvals since this is not a current quality indicator. The literature review was updated in September and November 2014, through CINAHL, PubMed, GoogleScholar, and Cochrane Library to assure currency of best practice techniques.

IRB Application and Approval

The application process for IRB approval at my local organization was very extensive. I worked closely with the IRB Administrator for the region. The first steps were to complete Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) training, research compliance training, and human subjects training. The certificates for completion of these courses were uploaded to the online system. The next step was to create user identification for online research information system (iRIS) at the hospital. It was then necessary to submit an application through iRIS detailing the project. The study application through iRIS had six sections that were filled out completely and accurately, and is described below.

General Information

This first section provided the basic information about the study such as the title, purpose, and location of my hospital from which the data was obtained. It also detailed whether or not the study would track research subjects or patients. Since I was solely interested in our 4-month incidence of epidural failures, I did not use individual patient

information. This section also documented which departments were involved in the study and whether multiple facilities were accessed.

Setup Department Access

This step involved setting up access to different hospital departments that were used in the study. For this project, only the obstetrical and anesthesia departments were involved. The obstetrical department was designated as the primary department. It was also necessary to report that my hospital is the sole facility where the data was accessed.

Grant Key Personnel Access to the Project

The third step involved assigning key study personnel to the project. Only one principal investigator could be designated. All additional personnel such as managers, research associates, and other staff were added as “research support staff.” Anyone added can access this project and receive notifications of any updates. Since I was the one conducting the study, I was designated as principal investigator.

Funding Information

This section required a selection of funding resources for this project. No funding resources were utilized.

Study Type: Research and Application Type

This section described the type of research being conducted. After a conversation with the IRB Administrator, it was determined that my project was “data only.” The responses to these questions prompted responses to certain sections of the IRB application.

Completion of Study Application

This section prompted additional questions based upon answers in previous sections. Here, all information was clarified and documents were added in order to submit the application in its entirety. These documents included the human subjects training certificate as well as other certificates required.

CSUF IRB Approval

Once my project received IRB approval from my hospital, it was submitted to the IRB at California State University, Fullerton for approval. Once it had been granted CSUF approval, data collection began in January 2015 to evaluate the 4-month incidence of epidural failures.

Chart Audits: Epidural Failure Rates

The data collection process involved accessing patient charts from an electronic medical record to determine the number of failed epidurals in a given 4-month period. Four months of data was collected in order to account for every provider at my facility (4 months reflects the staff assignment rotation). The data was collected from 2013; 4 consecutive months yielding the highest number of epidurals for the year (July, 2013-October, 2013). Lack of analgesia or one-side block requiring replacement of an epidural, the inability to use the epidural for surgical anesthesia, dural puncture, and intravenous catheters requiring an additional placement of an epidural catheter constituted a failure in epidural anesthesia. A data collection tool was used to assure measurement of epidural placement date, number in the delivery book (local), total number of punctures, and presence of any of the following that indicate failure: intravascular, one-sided, no analgesia, dural puncture, and failed surgical anesthesia.

Evidence Based Practice Protocol

The development of an evidence based practice guideline was done following a search and analysis of quality evidence (experimental studies, meta-analyses, or systematic reviews that evaluated techniques involved in epidural administration). Following creation of topical tables of evidence, practice recommendations were drawn from the evidence. A list of cited references is a part of the guideline.

Implementation/Evaluation

After the practice guidelines have been developed, the recommendations will be disseminated to staff anesthetists at my facility. DiCenso, Guyatt, and Ciliska (2005) described effective strategies that will be adopted to assist in the implementation of this practice guideline. Multiple interactive strategies will be used during implementation in order to improve the rate of compliance among providers (DiCenso et al., 2005).

In spring 2015, an information session during at least one regularly scheduled anesthesia meeting will allow time for the information to be presented as well as for a discussion among providers who may have questions or feel hesitant toward change. This meeting will include a report on the epidural failure rate chart audit results to aid in showing the significance of the problem locally.

A small printed laminated card with the recommendations and rationale will be given to all providers as a reminder tool. Finally, 12 months following the educational session, a follow-up meeting will be organized to report current epidural failure rates and the results will be placed in staff mailboxes. At this time, a discussion amongst colleagues will take place in order to reflect upon the success of this guideline implementation.

Evaluation of the effectiveness of the guideline on epidural failure rates will be performed after 1 year over the same 4-month period selected for baseline data to determine the success of the implementation. This will allow ample time for providers to consider the recommendations in the guideline, reflect on needed changes in their own practices, and hopefully, adopt new practice techniques, which improve their skills in epidural placement and management. A successful implementation will be evidenced by a decrease in the proportion of epidural failures based upon placements.

RESULTS

In this results section of this paper, the evidence that should drive current practice recommendations for anesthesia providers administering labor epidurals is evaluated. The factors under review included combined spinal epidural/dural puncture epidural technique, epidural needle placement/depth of catheter, epidural opioids/dosing regimen, epidural space identifier, multiport/uniport catheters, patient positioning, saline pre-distention of epidural space, and predictors of failed labor epidurals. A table of practice recommendations is shown based upon this synthesis (Table 1). A data collection tool is then shown (Table 2), followed by the baseline 4-month epidural medical record review (Table 3).

Current Practice Recommendations

Based upon the extensive literature review, a set of best practice techniques was developed. These techniques account for all eight factors under review and are described below.

Combined spinal epidural/dural puncture (see Appendix A for table of evidence)

- CSE and traditional epidural are equally effective for analgesia (Heesen et al., 2013; Norris et al., 1994).
- CSE provides quicker onset as compared to traditional epidural; however, is associated with side effects such as itching and nausea and vomiting (Gambling et al., 2013; Norris et al., 1994).

- DPE technique improves spread of local anesthetic and quickens onset of relief (Cappiello et al., 2008, Suzuki, Koganemaru, Onizuka, S., & Takasaki, 1996).

Epidural needle placement/depth of catheter (see Appendix B for table of evidence)

- The bevel of the epidural needle affects the spread of local anesthetic into the epidural space; the bevel should face the intended area to be blocked with local anesthetic (Borghi et al., 2004; Huffnagle et al., 1998).
- Epidural catheters should be threaded 3-5 cm into the epidural space in order to decrease intravascular cannulation and improve success of analgesia (Beilin et al., 2000; Mhyre et al., 2009; Muppuri et al., 2012).

Epidural opioids/dosing regimen (see Appendix C for table of evidence)

- Fentanyl co-administered with local anesthetic epidurally is 3 times as potent as when administered intravenously suggesting a spinal mechanism of action (Ginosar et al., 2003).
- Programmed intermittent epidural bolus technique results in less total local anesthetic consumption, improved patient satisfaction, decreased anesthetic interventions, and superior analgesia as compared to continuous infusions with patient controlled anesthesia (Capogna et al., 2011; George et al., 2013; Halpern et al., 2004; Sia, Leo, & Ocampo, 2013; Sia, Lim, & Ocampo, 2007, Wong et al., 2011; Wong et al., 2006).

Epidural space identifier (see Appendix D for table of evidence)

- Loss of resistance tests using both air and saline both provide adequate analgesia (Sanford, Rodriguez, Schmidt, & Austin, 2013; Schier et al., 2009; Segal & Arendt 2010).
- Loss of resistance to air is associated with risk of pneumocephalus and venous air embolus (Katz, Markovits, & Rosenberg, 1990; Naulty, Ostheimer, Datta, Knapp, & Weiss, 1982).
- Loss of resistance to saline is superior due to low complication risk (Agaram et al., 2007; Beilin et al., 2000; Katz et al., 1990; Muppurri et al., 2012; Naulty et al., 1982; Sanford et al., 2013; Segal & Arendt, 2010; Shenouda & Cunningham, 2003).

Multiport/uniport catheters (see Appendix E for table of evidence)

- Multiport catheters act as single port catheters on infusion pumps but act as multiport catheters when manual boluses are administered (Fegley, Lerman, & Wissler, 2008).
- Multiport catheters improve spread of local anesthetic and decrease inadequate analgesia and catheter manipulation (D'Angelo et al., 1997; Michael, Richmond, & Birks, 1989; Segal, Eappen, & Datta, 1997).
- Multiport catheters are associated with a higher risk of intravascular cannulation (Mhyre et al., 1989).

Patient positioning (see Appendix F for table of evidence)

- Placing the epidural catheter with the patient in the lateral position decreases intravascular cannulation probably due to reduced venous congestion (Bahar et al., 2004; Mhyre et al., 2009).
- Epidural catheters can migrate with patient position changes, especially in obese patients; therefore, taping the catheter with the patient in the lateral position yields highest success (Hamilton, Riley, & Cohen, 1997).

Saline pre-distension of epidural space (see Appendix G for table of evidence)

- Epidural vessels are engorged in first trimester and venous congestion increases in the third trimester putting the patient at risk for intravascular cannulation (Igarashi et al., 2000).
- Intravascular cannulation is greatly reduced with saline pre-distention of 5-10 ml prior to catheter insertion (Evron et al., 2007; Gadalla et al., 2003; Geng, Sun, & Huang, 2014; Mhyre et al., 2009).
- Soft tip epidural catheters reduce intravascular cannulation, dural puncture, and paresthesias (Shih et al., 2012).

Predictors of failed labor analgesia (see Appendix H for table of evidence)

- Risk factors for inadequate analgesia from labor epidurals include a history of a failed epidural, cervical dilation > 7 cm, difficult palpation of interspinous space, spinal deformity, inability to flex the back, and obesity (Agaram et al., 2007; Guglielminotti et al., 2013; Hollister, Todd, Ball, Thorp-Jones, & Coghill, 2012; Muppuri et al., 2012; Pan et al., 2004; Withington & Weeks 1994).

- The major risk factor for failed surgical anesthesia is having to deliver additional manual boluses to maintain labor analgesia (Bauer et al., 2012; Riley & Papasin, 2001).
- Ultrasound can improve the success rate of labor analgesia in patients who have risk factors for failed analgesia (Muppuri et al., 2012; Vallejo et al., 2010).

Table 1

Epidural Placement Recommendations

Epidural placement variable	Evidence based recommendation	Rationale
Combined Spinal/Epidural & Dural Puncture Epidural	CSE and DPE provide a more rapid onset than traditional labor epidural; DPE is associated with less pruritis, nausea, and vomiting as compared to CSE.	Local anesthetic and narcotic injected into the subarachnoid space provides a rapid onset as compared to epidural analgesia. Side effects of these medications in the subarachnoid space include itching, nausea, and vomiting.
Epidural Needle Bevel Orientation & Depth of Catheter	Bevel should be facing cephalad in order to provide a bilateral block; epidural catheter should be threaded 3-5 cm into epidural space.	The direction of the bevel affects the spread of local anesthetic and should be facing the direction of the desired block. Epidural catheters threaded greater than 5 cm into space increase risk of intravascular cannulation and one-sided blocks. Epidural catheters threaded less than 3 cm into space have an increased risk of falling out.
Epidural Opioids/Dosing Regimen	Local anesthetics should be administered as a bolus rather than as a continuous infusion and narcotics should be co-administered.	Fentanyl administered epidurally is 3 times as potent as when it is administered intravenously. Local anesthetics delivered as a programmed intermittent bolus decreases total consumption of local anesthetic and improves analgesia as compared to a continuous infusion.
Epidural Space Identifier	Saline and air are both adequate for analgesia, however saline is a safer technique.	Air is associated with risk of pneumocephalus and venous air embolus. Contraindications to using air include epidural blood patch, and repeat epidural after a positive dural puncture due to the possible communication of air into the subarachnoid space.

Table 1. Continued

Epidural placement variable	Evidence based recommendation	Rationale
Multiport/Uniport Catheters	Multiport catheters improve spread of local anesthetic and should be administered as intermittent boluses.	Multiport catheters act as single port catheters when a continuous infusion pump is utilized. Programmed intermittent boluses allow all three ports to be used, thus improving spread of local anesthetic and improving patient analgesia.
Patient Positioning	Lateral positioning decreases intravascular cannulation and migration of catheter. Taping the catheter in the lateral position decreases catheter movement.	Epidural veins are engorged during pregnancy, placing the patient at risk for intravascular cannulation. The lateral position decreases this engorgement. In obese patients the catheter has the potential to migrate up to 4cm with position changes. This is reduced when the catheter is taped with the patient in the lateral position.
Saline Pre-distension of Epidural Space	5-10ml of saline pre-distention of the epidural space greatly decreases intravascular cannulation.	Epidural vessels are engorged during pregnancy and the pre-distention of saline helps to displace vessels and aides in the threading of the catheter.
Predictors of Epidural Failures	Obesity, scoliosis, and previous failed epidural are risk factors of failed epidural analgesia. Increased boluses to maintain labor analgesia is major risk factor for failed surgical anesthesia.	Difficult anatomy leads to difficult epidural placement. A previously failed epidural may give insight to anatomical deformities that cannot be observed on the outside. Ultrasound may be helpful in these situations to identify correct placement of epidural needle.

Table 2

Epidural Failures Audit Tool

Date	Number in Delivery Book	Intravascular	One-sided	No analgesia	Dural puncture	Failed surgical anesthesia	Total number of punctures

Epidural Failure (July 2013-September 2013)

During the 4-month chart audit of 559 labor epidurals at my facility, 46 showed evidence of at least one factor contributing to a failed anesthesia experience (see Table

3). This yielded an approximate 8.2% failed epidural rate. The most common factor was a lack of analgesia, in which the patient had to have the epidural catheter replaced.

Difficult patient anatomy, failed surgical anesthesia, one-sided blocks, and unintentional dural punctures were all close in frequency. Of note, there was only one intravascular catheter placed, and one event of a pneumocephalus with loss of resistance to air technique

Table 3

Factors Leading to Epidural Failures

Factor	N (%)
Intravascular	1 (0.2%)
One-sided	7 (1.3%)
No analgesia	20 (3.6%)
Dural puncture	5 (0.8%)
Failed surgical anesthesia	6 (1.1%)
Other	7 (1.3%)
# of punctures	
1	515
2	36
3+	8

Total Failures: 46/559 = 8.2% failure rate.

DISCUSSION

The epidural failure rate at my facility was about 8%. While no concrete evidence exists for best practice statistics, this failure rate can be decreased. Therefore, improvements in techniques are needed to decrease this rate and improve patient analgesia and satisfaction. Based upon the results from Table 3, the major causes of epidural failure at my local hospital were one-sided blocks, no analgesia, and failed surgical anesthesia. Recommendations for practice changes that would influence these problems will be emphasized during the practice guideline implementation. One-sided blocks and lack of analgesia necessitate the need for replacing the epidural catheter. This results in the obstetric patient continuing to suffer in pain and provides a stressful experience for the patient, family, and anesthesia provider (Heesen et al., 2013). Failed conversion of labor analgesia to surgical anesthesia can present a life-threatening risk to the obstetrical patient. In this circumstance, two options are available: (a) place a subarachnoid block or (b) put the patient under general anesthesia.

One-Sided Blocks

One-sided blocks occur when a patient has analgesia on one side and pain on the opposite side. Epidural needle rotation is one factor affecting unilateral epidural blocks. Borghi and colleagues looked at epidural bevel rotation on unilateral blocks for patients undergoing total hip arthroplasty. The results showed that rotating the bevel 45 degrees toward the operative side provided a preferential distribution of both sensory and motor block (Borghi et al., 2004). Therefore, the bevel of the epidural needle should be placed cephalad in order to produce a bilateral block in an obstetric patient (Borghi et al., 2004).

Improper placement of the epidural catheter within the epidural space is a main cause of one-sided blocks (Beilin et al., 2000). The position of the catheter in the epidural space is quite often suboptimal (Beilin et al., 2000). While only a small portion of epidural catheters go the intended cephalad direction, many others end up in an undesired location. The catheters may form a terminal loop, coil at the insertion site, or migrate out through an intervertebral foramen. Therefore, an epidural catheter should be threaded the least amount of distance into the epidural space in order to decrease this likelihood of malposition. Beilin et al. (2000) found that epidural catheters threaded about 5 cm into the epidural space yielded better patient analgesia than those placed deeper or shallower into the space. Catheters threaded 7 cm yielded more one-sided blocks and intravenous punctures, and catheters threaded 3 cm had a few dislodgements occur.

Hamilton et al. (1997) looked at changes in the position of the catheter with patient movement. They looked at the position of unsecured epidural catheters relative to the skin as the patients moved from the sitting flexed to sitting upright and lateral positions. With each subsequent position change, the catheter moved further into the epidural space and was drawn into the skin. Catheter movement was directly correlated with the patient's body mass index: the higher the BMI, the further the catheter was drawn in. However, even in the lowest BMI group (< 25) a maximum change of 1.9 cm was observed. In one obese parturient, the observed movement was greater than 4 cm. If the epidural catheter is placed and taped in the sitting position and the patient then moves to the lateral position, the catheter has the potential to move out as it is now being held by the adhesive tape. Taping the catheter after the patient has relaxed the spine can decrease

catheter movement. It is recommended that epidural catheters be taped in the lateral position, and this is especially important in morbidly obese patients, where catheter movement is more pronounced.

Lack of Analgesia

Lack of analgesia in obstetric patients can occur with inappropriate catheter location, kinking or occlusion of catheter, or migration (Muppuri et al., 2012). Unfortunately this leads to maternal dissatisfaction and ineffective anesthesia in the operative suite. The CSE technique is one option that may benefit the obstetric patient. CSE technique provides rapid analgesia, minimal motor blockade, and also verifies close proximity of the epidural space (Cappiello et al., 2008). While it provides superior analgesia, some drawbacks include hemodynamic changes, fetal heart rate descent, and the inability to adequately assess the function of the epidural catheter (Cappiello et al., 2008). Norris and colleagues compared the complications of both techniques and found that women who received CSE instead of traditional epidurals complained of more pruritis, nausea, and vomiting. However, dural puncture was more common in the epidural group (4.2% vs. 1.7%) and the incidence of hypotension was the same between the groups (Norris et al., 1994).

The DPE technique is emerging in obstetrical anesthesia because it has benefits of the CSE technique without the side effects of hemodynamic changes. The benefits of the DPE technique include more rapid analgesia, verification of epidural space vicinity, better hemodynamic stability, and the ability to assess the functionality of the epidural catheter (Cappiello et al., 2008). Suzuki and colleagues (1996) evaluated the spread of analgesia induced by epidural injection of local anesthetic after a dural puncture with a

26-gauge needle and found that there was a marked increase in caudal spread of analgesia. There was no difference in spread of local anesthetic in the cephalad direction (Suzuki et al., 1996).

Finally, in the 4-month audit, seven patients who received multiple punctures were due to “other” issues such as patient anatomy. Guglielminotti et al. (2013) looked at characteristics of patients that yielded difficult epidural placements and found three major risk factors: (a) inability to palpate the spinous process, (b) spinal deformity, and (c) inability for the patient to properly sit (Guglielminotti et al., 2013). This correlates with the data at my hospital, as the patients who received multiple punctures had either scoliosis, difficult anatomy, and/or obesity. One solution to a patient with difficult anatomy is the use of ultrasound to assist with placement. Vallejo et al. (2010) looked at the use of ultrasound by resident trainees placing labor epidurals to determine if it decreased the failure rate. They found that the use of ultrasound both improved the success of the labor epidural and decreased the number of attempts or punctures by the trainees (Vallejo et al., 2010). Ultrasound use may not always be practical, as it requires training; however being cognizant of difficult epidural placements can help the anesthetist adequately prepare and inform the patient of realistic expectations.

Failed Surgical Anesthesia

Failure to convert epidural analgesia to surgical anesthesia places the patient at an increased risk for morbidity and mortality (Bauer et al., 2012). Two options for surgical anesthesia are to place a subarachnoid block or to put the patient under general anesthesia. Neither option is favorable as both are associated with an increase risk to the patient. A spinal block placed after an epidural puts the patient at increased risk of

developing a total spinal, necessitating immediate intubation (Riley & Papasin, 2001). General anesthesia places the pregnant patient at risk for aspiration, difficult intubation, and fetal depression (Riley & Papasin, 2001). While failed surgical anesthesia only accounted for 1.1% of all epidurals placed in the 4-month audit, this does not represent the failure rate of epidurals that failed surgically. At my hospital, six out of 34 epidurals failed to convert to surgical anesthesia, an approximately 18% failure rate for conversion to surgical anesthesia. The Royal College of Anaesthetists deemed that there should be a less than 1% conversion rate for elective cesarean sections and < 3% conversion rate for emergency sections. Therefore, this is an area that needs a lot of improvement within our department. Bauer et al. (2012) and Riley and Papasin (2001) looked at risk factors associated with failed conversion of epidural analgesia to surgical anesthesia. Both studies found that the main risk factor for failed epidural conversion was an increase in the number of manual boluses the patient requested. An increase in the usual amount of local anesthetic to maintain patient analgesia may be a sign that the epidural is not working well, and should be replaced in order to prevent an anesthetic emergency (Riley & Papasin, 2001).

Pneumocephalus

A pneumocephalus is a rare complication of epidural anesthesia in which air is injected into the subarachnoid space causing a severe headache for the patient. Treatment involves oxygen therapy and intravenous analgesics and typically resolves quicker than a post dural puncture headache (Shenouda & Cunningham, 2003). While this is a very rare complication of epidural anesthesia, the consequences can be very debilitating for patients. Computed tomography will confirm this diagnosis by observation of an air-

filled cavity in a region of the brain (Katz et al., 1990). One patient at my hospital developed a suspected pneumocephalus, which was characterized by an extreme headache as soon as the patient lay supine. A known dural puncture had occurred just before this with a documented loss of resistance to air technique. Katz et al. (1990) described a similar instance; however it was in an unknown dural puncture. The patient, however, developed severe transient neurological symptoms and on computed tomography (CT) there was an approximately 25 ml air-filled cavity noted in the parietofrontal cerebral cortex of the brain (Katz et al., 1990). The pneumocephalus resolved spontaneously by the next day; however, the patient had to undergo extensive neurological monitoring (Katz et al., 1990).

Loss of resistance to air technique should be used with caution due to complications associated with this technique (Katz et al., 1990). Naulty et al. (1982) described the risk for venous air embolism in patients receiving epidurals with loss of resistance to air. Two conditions need to exist for a patient to have a venous air embolism. First, an opening in a vein must occur in which air can enter, such as by a puncture with an epidural needle. Second, the pressure of the source of the air must be higher than that of the vein, such as by a manual bolus of air during loss of resistance technique. While all patients being studied had clinically insignificant side effects, there has been a reported venous air embolism case after 2.5 ml of air was used for determination of loss of resistance (Shenouda & Cunningham, 2003).

Finally, loss of resistance technique to air technique is cautioned in situations that could lead to a pneumocephalus. For example, when an epidural blood patch is administered for treatment of a known dural puncture, saline is preferred because there

can be some communication of air into the subarachnoid space through the puncture hole. This same theory applies when repeating an epidural for a known dural puncture). Due to its risk of complications, saline should be utilized for loss of resistance technique (Beilin et al., 2000).

Implications for Practice

A 4-month chart audit at my facility revealed areas that are in need of improvement regarding epidural techniques. Evidence-based recommendations on best practice techniques will be given to the CRNA's and MDA's at my facility. An in-service is scheduled for April 2, 2015, where the recommendations will be given following a discussion of epidural failure rates at my facility. These will encompass all eight factors that were under review in order to improve the success rate of patient analgesia with labor epidurals. Patient failure rates will be re-evaluated 1 year after implementation of these guidelines to assess the success rate of this initiative. The goal is that both patient analgesia and satisfaction are improved in our obstetrical department.

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APPENDIX A

TABLE OF EVIDENCE: COMBINED SPINAL EPIDURAL/DURAL PUNCTURE

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
Compare DPE to traditional EPI tech for labor analg. Cappiello et al. (2008)	Prospective, double-blind RCT. IDV: DPE w/ or w/o IT drug administration. DV: labor analg.	80 nulliparous women w/ cerv dil < 5cm, randomly assigned to EPI placement w/ or w/o DPE. EC: No leaking CSF.	Sensory level (1-sided or 2-sided) and VAS analgesia score.	SS findings: DPE grp had faster sacral dermatome blockade; had ↓ VAS scores.	DP immediately before EPI anes improves spread, onset, & bilateral pain in nulliparous women.
Evaluate pain scores of laboring women receiving CSE vs EPI anes. Gambling et al. (2013)	RCT IDV: CSE vs EPI analg. DV: pain, PCEA use, # EPI top-up doses, # cath replacements, SE, labor outcomes.	Sharp Mary Birch Hospital for Women & Newborns (n = 402). IC: ability to speak & understand Eng, ASA I-III, term labor w/o complications, req neuraxial analg. EC: inabil to speak/understand Eng, ASA > III, preterm gestation, breech, previous C/S, multiple gestations, uterine or cervical surgery, BMI > 40.	VRPS (0-10) in beginning of labor and after delivery; overall satisfaction (0-4); pruritis assessed on verbal scale (0-10); motor block assessed (1-5).	Pts in CSE grp had better analg in beginning (1.4 vs 1.9, <i>p</i> < .001); complete anes was quicker in CSE grp though not SS.	CSE tech provides quicker onset as compared to EPI analg. Limit: inconsistency with design.
To determine the differences in success	Meta-analysis review of databases CINAHL,	10 RCTs, 1722 pts.	No globally accepted definitions so each	RR reported as CSE vs EPI; for replacement was 0.57; 1-sided block	CSE and EPI equally safe and effective; reporter bias may have

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
rates between CSE and EPI for laboring pts. Heesen et al. (2013)	LILACE, CENTRAL, & ISI WOS. DV: EPI cath replacement, 1-sided block, IV cannulation, and # of boluses required.	2 authors reviewed articles; 90 articles met criteria. IC: randomized single or double blind, compared CSE w/ EPI, discussed 1-sided blocks, # of boluses, # of replacements, or IV placement.	author's definitions were used.	0.48; however $I^2 = .69$, $p = .01$ suggesting strong similarity in studies; EPI boluses was 0.95; IV placement was 1.71; all had CI 95%; Only SS finding: one sided blocks; however strong between-study similarity.	been an issue; no blinding of provider; definitions between studies varied; no control for experience of provider; single blind has more bias.
To determine the complications associated w/ CLE and CSE. Norris et al. (1994)	Prospective evaluation of 1022 pts. IDV: CLE or CSE. DV: accidental DP, high level, low BP, use of vasopressors, itching, nausea and vomiting.	Thomas Jefferson University Hospital 924 pts: 388 req CLE, 536 req CSE. IC: admitted to labor suite with expected vaginal delivery. EC: none.	Low BP (SBP < 100mmHg); itching as a spontaneous complaint or active scratching.	CSE pts reported more itching (41.4% vs 1.3%), nausea (2.4% vs 1.0%) and vomiting (3.2% vs 1.0%) than CLE grp; DP occurred more frequently in CLE grp (4.2% vs 1.7%).	Both CLE and CSE provide effective analg, however each is associated with risks. Limit: self-selection of pts to grps.
To determine the effect of DP with a 26-g needle of the spread of analg from EPI injection of LA. Suzuki et al. (1996)	RCT. IDV: DP w/ 26-g needle at L2-L3 or none. DV: spread of analg.	40 pts. IC: ASA I or II scheduled for lower abdominal surgery. EC: DM or neurologic disease.	Spread of analg assessed by pinprick at 5, 10, 15, 20 mins post injection of 15 ml dose; dermatome level assessed on left side of body.	Caudal spread of analg sig ↑ in DP grp 15 and 20 min post injection.	DP w/ 26-g needle ↑ caudal spread of analg induced by LA.

Notes: analg = analgesia; anes = anesthesia; ASA = American Society of Anesthesiologists; BP = blood pressure; BMI = body mass index; cath = catheter; cerv = cervical; cm = centimeters; CSF = cerebrospinal fluid; C/S = cesarean section; CI = confidence interval; CLE = continuous lumbar epidural; CSE = combined spinal/epidural; ↓ = decreased/less; DV = dependent variable; DM = diabetes mellitus; dil = dilation; DP = dural puncture; DPE = dural puncture epidural; EC = exclusion criteria; Eng = English; EPI = epidural; g = gauge; inabil = inability; IC = inclusion criteria; ↑ = increased/greater; IDV = independent variable; IT = intrathecal; IV = intravascular; LA = local anesthetic; L2 = lumbar 2; L3 = lumbar 3; ml = milliliter; min = minute; PCEA =

programmed continuous epidural anesthesia; pt = patient; RCT = randomized controlled trial; RR = relative risk; req = requesting; SE = side effects; SS = statistically significant; SBP = systolic blood pressure; tech = technique; VAS = visual analog scale; VRPS = verbal rating pain scale; vs = versus; w/ = with; w/o = without.

APPENDIX B

TABLE OF EVIDENCE: EPIDURAL NEEDLE PLACEMENT/DEPTH OF CATHETER

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
Determine the optimal distance an EPI cath should be left in the space. Beilin et al. (2000)	Prospective, randomized, double blind study. IDV: 3, 5, or 7cm. DV: adequate analg.	100 women in active labor, contracting every 5 min, req an EPI; 3 grps. EC: sp column disorders, sp surgery.	Analg = pain at peak of contraction; sensory blockade = perception of cold; failed = no sensory blockade; incomplete = missed segments.	Highest IV incidence in 7cm grp ($p < .05$), lowest rate of incomplete analg in 5cm grp ($p < .05$). 1 failed block 3 hr post placement in 3cm grp, cath may have dislodged.	Women w/ multiorifice caths threaded 5cm into EPI space had highest success of adequate analg. Lower rate of complications also seen in 5cm grp as compared to 7cm grp.
To evaluate the effects of needle bevel orientation on EPI block. Borghi et al. (2004)	Prospective, RCT. IDV: needle bevel orientation; 45 degree and 90 degree (control grp). DV: distribution of LA.	48 pts ASA I-III req EPI anes for THR; 2 grps; 45 degree rotation grp and 90 degree rotation grp. EC: C/I to EPI anes, previous back surgery, DM, or severe CV or respiratory disease.	Sensation and motor block bilateral; quality of analg; volume of LA used in first 48 hrs.	Max sensory level was T10 in control grp, T9 in 45 degree grp; max sensory level on non-operative side was T10 in control grp and L3 in 45 degree grp ($p = 0.0005$); movement gone sooner in 45 degree grp than ctrl grp; 45 degree grp used ↓ LA ($p = .0005$).	Rotation of bevel toward operative side provides preferential distribution of sensory and motor block and less LA utilized.
Determine the effect of EPI needle bevel orientation on success of EPI analg. Huffnagle et al. (1998)	Randomized, prospective, double-blind study. IDV: bevel needle orientation. DV: sensory blockade	160 ASA I or II term women req EPI analg; Grp 0 = 0 rotation directing bevel to pts left; Grp 90 = rotated 90° to right; directing bevel down; Grp 180 = rotation 180° to right	Bilat sensory levels to cold, comfort level. If inadeq analg then determined if 1-sided, no block, or inadeq bilateral block.	EPI needle rotation not assoc w/ DP risk; Cath hard to pass in grp 180 ($p < .01$). 1-sided analg ↓ in grp 90, more blocks were symmetrical and higher	Entering the space w/ bevel parallel and rotating 90° downward is effective, easy, and provides better labor analg.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
		directing bevel to pts right; Grp 270 = rotation 270° clockwise directing bevel down. EC: prior sp surgeries or hardware.		% of pts were comfortable.	
Evaluate strategies to ↓ EPI vein cannulation. Mhyre et al. (2009)	Systematic review. IDV: depth of cath insertion. DV: risk of IV placement with EPI cath.	Medline, EMBASE, Cochrane, & CINAHL databases searched, 2 RCTs included; Eng language between 1984-2007, n = 884.	Rate of IV cath cannulation.	Cath insertion depths < 6cm ↓ IV EPI cannulation compared to 7cm or > (15.2% vs 5.4%).	Limiting EPI cath depth to 6cm or less ↓ IV cannulation; the definition for IV cannulation was widely varied.
Examine the effect of a multitude of factors that contribute to inadeq pain relief from labor EPI. Muppuri et al. (2012)	Prospective, OBS study IDVs: length of EPI cath left in space. DV: Inadeq labor EPI anes.	University Women's Hospital; 502 laboring women req a labor EPI for pain mgmt. EC: rapid progress to 2 nd stage or delivery & pts whose EPI was not in EPI space: sp tap or IV placement; monitored cont.	Pain = VPS 30 min post EPI placement (0-100) with 0 = no pain; 100 = bad pain; pain = uterine or back pain assoc w/ contractions; VPS > 10 considered inadeq anes.	Predictor SS: hx failed EPI ($p = .001$), multiparity vs primiparity ($p = .021$), air vs saline for LOR ($p = .020$), cervical dilation > 7cm ($p = .001$), Pitocin usage ($p = .012$), induction of labor ($p = .023$), & parasthesia during placement ($p = .001$). Best predictors of inadeq EPI anes: hx of failed EPI, cervical dilation > 7cm, parasthesia, LOR using air.	Pts at high risk may benefit from appropriate length of EPI cath remaining in space.

Notes: analg = analgesia; anes = anesthesia; ASA = American Society of Anesthesiologists; assoc. = associated; aug = augmented; CV = cardiovascular; cath. = catheter; C/I = contraindication; cm = centimeters; ↓ = decreased/less; DV = dependent variable; DM = diabetes mellitus; DP = dural puncture; Eng = English; EC = exclusion criteria; EPI = epidural; grp = group; hr = hour; hx = history; IDV = independent variable; inadeq = inadequate; ↑ = increased/greater; IV = intravascular; LA = local anesthetic; L3 = lumbar 3; LOR = loss of resistance; mgmt = management; min = minute; OBS = observational; pt = patient; RCT = randomized control trial; req = requesting; sp = spinal; SS = statistically significant; T9 = thoracic 9; T10 = thoracic 10; THR = total hip replacement; VPS = verbal pain scale; vs = versus; w/ = with.

APPENDIX C

TABLE OF EVIDENCE: EPIDURAL OPIOIDS/DOSING REGIMEN

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
To compare the incidence of motor block and mode of delivery in women receiving PIEB and CEI for maintenance of labor analg. Capogna et al. (2011).	Prospective, randomized, double blind study. IDV: PIEB + PCEA (grp PIEB) or CEI + PCEA (grp CEI). DV: maternal motor function and mode of delivery.	145 healthy, nulliparous, term women delivering at Citta di Roma Hospital, Roma. IC: singleton, vertex pregnancies in spon labor. EC: preg disorder, breech or multiple gestation, taking opioids, requiring oxytocin, or unable to perform motor block.	Degree of motor block assessed bilaterally in LE using Bromage score; number of PCEA bolus doses and total LA solution utilized also recorded.	Motor block was 37% in CEI grp vs 2.7% in PIEB grp ($p < .001$); motor block occurred earlier ($p = .008$) and was more common at complete cerv dil ($p < .001$) in CEI grp; forceps required 20% vs 7% ($p = .03$) in CEI grp; total LA used, number of bolus requests, and number of PCEA boluses were lower in PIEB grp ($p < .001$).	Analg maintenance with PIEB resulted in ↓ motor blockade, ↓ forcep deliveries, and ↓ total LA consumption.
To compare intermittent EPI bolus vs continuous EPI infusion on labor analgesia. George et al. (2013)	Systematic review & meta-analysis. IDV: IEB and standard CEI w/ or w/o PCEA DV: pt satisfaction & need for anes intervention	9 RCT's, 344 women got CEI, 350 received IEB analg; 5 databases utilized. IC: RCTs comparing IEB with CEI dosing w/ or w/o PCEA	VRS & VAS used to measure pt satisfaction (0-100); EPI dose = total volume/hrs of labor; all LAs used were converted to mg equivalents of bupiv; data analyzed using random effects model.	SS decrease in LA volume w/ IEB; increased maternal satisfaction w/ IEB.	IEB decreases total LA volume used, increases pt satisfaction and decreased anes interventions. Limit: inconsistency in reporting outcomes among studies, wide heterogeneity among studies, no standardization w/ dosing regimens.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
To determine the analg effect of fent admin through an EPI cath. Ginosar et al. (2003)	Prospective, randomized, double-blinded study. IDV: IV fent and EPI fent. DV: analgesia.	48 women at Stanford University Hospitals. IC: nulliparity, early active labor, cerv dil < 5cm, req for EPI, 18-40 years, ASA I or II, body weight < 110kg, term, singleton, vertex presentation. EC: opioids in prev 3hrs, uterine surgery, preeclampsia, inabil to understand consent.	Success: no addl analg req until > 8cm therefore next pt would receive 0.01% weight/volume ↓; failure: supplemental analg up to 12ml bupiv needed to provide analg when < 8cm therefore next pt would receive 0.01% weight/volume ↑; reject: 12ml bupiv did not relieve pain and most likely cath problem, therefore next pt would receive same dose; VAPS measured hrly (0-100); pruritits, n/v, and satisfaction measured 1hr after delivery on VAS (0-100).	The MLAC of bupiv w/ IV fent was 0.063 and w/ EPI fent was 0.019; relative potency ratio for EPI/IV was 3.3($p = .0017$); pruritis was greater in EPI fent grp ($p = .005$).	When co-admin w/ bupiv EPI fent is 3x as potent as IV fent therefore highly suggestive of a sp mechanism of action; when co-admin w/ fent there is a marked LA sparing effect. Limitations: no VAPS before enrollment; possible selection bias.
To compare efficacy of PCEA to IV analg. Halpern et al. (2004)	Multicenter, RCT. IDV: PCEA vs PCIA. DV: labor outcomes/pt satisfaction/labor analg.	Nulliparous pts w/ healthy term females; 2 grps: 1 st grp received PCIA, 2 nd grp PCEA (n = 242). IC: regular contractions, 3cm dil & effaced. EC: preeclampsia, hemorrhage, BMI >35, multiple gestation, abn	VAS measured q 2hr during 1 st stage labor and q 30min during 2 nd stage labor; motor block w/ mod Bromage scale (1-6); maternal satisfaction with VAS; SE such as resp depression, drowsiness, fever, n/v during labor.	More pts required antiemetics in PCIA grp compared to PCEA grp (17% vs 6.4%) ($p = .01$), pts were more sedated in PCIA grp (39% vs 5%)($p < .001$); maternal satisfaction was ↑ in PCEA grp (7.7 vs 6.8) ($p = .02$); more infants required resuscitation in PCIA	Women in PCEA grp were significantly more satisfied w/ analg than in PCIA most likely d/t ↓ nausea, drowsiness and better analg. Inadeq analg was reason 39 pts in PCIA grp requested EPI; need for narcan and neonatal resuscitation was higher in PCIA grp.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
		presentation, fetal anomaly, fetal distress.		grp (61 of 118 vs 38 of 124) ($p = .001$).	Limit: no blinding of clinician or pt; many in PCIA requested add'l pain relief, ideal sample size not achieved.
To determine the analgesic efficacy using 3 different dosing regimens. Lim et al. (2008)	Prospective, randomized, double blind study. IDV: demand only PCEA vs PCEA w/ background infusion. DV: BTP.	300 pts req labor anes; 3 grps: grp 0: demand only PCEA, 5ml bolus, 15min lock; grp 5: 5ml/hr infusion, 5 ml bolus, 12min lock; grp 10: 10ml/hr infusion, 5ml bolus, 10min lock. IC: ASA I-II, > 18 y/o, full term, single fetus, < 5cm dilation, abil to use PCEA pump. EC: opioids < 3hr prior or taking chronic. opioids.	BTP = inadeq pain relief necessitating intervention by anes provider; VAS pain scores (0-10) scale.	Incid of BTP & VAS pain scores ↑ in grp 0(43%) vs grp 5(17%) and grp 10(11%) ($p < .001$); grp 10 had longer analg (895 min) as compared to grp 0(565 min)($p < .001$).	Demand only PCEA had ↓ LA consumed but more BTP, ↑ VAS scores, shorter pain relief, and ↓ pt satisfaction.
To determine analg efficacy using 2 different dosing regimens. Sia et al. (2013)	RCT. IDV: automated bolus group or infusion group. DV: BTP.	102 pts req labor analg; 2 grps: automated bolus grp: 5 ml mandated bolus 1-4 times/hr depending on analg demands of prev hr; infusion grp: 5 ml/hr basal infusion with PCEA 5ml bolus. IC: ASA I, full term, single fetus, dil < 5cm.	VAS pain scores (0-10) with > 3 = BTP; maternal satisfaction (0-100 scale).	BTP much ↓ in automated bolus grp (5.9%) than infusion grp (23.5%) ($p = .023$); ↑ pt satisfaction in automated bolus grp (96.5) vs infusion grp (89.2, $p < .001$).	Automated boluses provide superior analg as compared to background infusions w/ PCEA as they resulted in ↓ BTP, ↑ pt sat, and no ↑ in LA consumption.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
		EC: mult fetuses, breech, OB complications, C/I to EPI anes, opioids < 2hr.			
To determine the amount of LA used when 2 different EPI dosing regimens were utilized. Sia et al. (2007)	RCT IDV: PCEA + AMB vs PCEA + BCI. DV: LA consumption.	42 labor pts req EPI anes; 2 grps: PCEA + BCI 5ml/hr, 5ml bolus, 20ml max dose/hr; PCEA + AMB 5 ml/hr q hr, 5ml bolus, 20ml max dose/hr. IC: ASA I, non breech, full term, dil < 5cm. EC: opioids < 4hr, C/I to EPI, breech, prematurity, OB complications.	VAPS scale 0-10, 0 = no pain, 10 = worst pain; pt satisfaction VAS scale (0-100).	There was a ↓ in hrly consumption in PCEA + AMB grp (6.5ml vs 7.5ml, $p = .011$); more pts in PCEA + AMB grp did not self-bolus (6/21 vs 1/21, $p = .03$); time to first self-bolus was longer in PCEA + AMB grp (315min vs 190min, $p = .04$); no difference in pain scores or SE.	PCEA + AMB ↓ analg consumption and improved pt satisfaction although not SS.
To determine intermittent bolus time and total volume injected on labor analg. Wong et al. (2011)	Randomized, double blind study. IDV: programmed intermittent interval and amount of LA. DV: total drug use, quality of analg, pt satisfaction.	Healthy, term, nulliparous women in labor or w/ ruptured membranes who req neuraxial analg ($n = 180$). EC: systemic disease, chronic opioid use, use of opioids prior to analg, or cerv dil < 2 or > 5cm, delivery w/in 90 min of IT analg.	VAS score assessed 10 min post IT analg, randomized into 1 of 3 grps: 2.5ml q 15min 5ml q 30min or 10ml q 60min; VAS scores assessed q 120min until delivery; modified Bromage score determined q 120min (0 – 3); bilat sensory level to ice; pt satisfaction w/ analg (0–100).	Grp 10/60 consumed less bupiv; median consumption of bupiv/hr was 0.9mg ↓ in grp 10ml q 60 next to grp 5/30 and 0.8mg ↓ compared to grp 5ml q30 ($p = .18$); mean diff in bupiv consumption in grp 10ml q 60 was -1 and -1.2 respectively compared to grp 2.5ml q 15 and grp 5ml q 30 ($p = .002$, $p = .02$).	PIB tech results in ↓ bupiv consumption and improved pt satisfaction; this study shows that analg total may be due to dosing and vol of boluses. Limit: conclusions limited to pt population, drug concentration, & mode of initiation of labor analg.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
To determine the effect of EPI bolus vs continuous infusion on labor analg.	Randomized, double blind study. IDV: PEIB vs CEI.	126 women delivering at Northwestern University Hospital. IC: healthy, parous, term females w/ 1 baby, head down pregnancy, scheduled for induction. EC: presence of systemic disease and chronic opioid use.	VAS used for measuring pain (0-100), modified Bromage scale measured motor blockade (0-3), and VAS scale for overall satisfaction (0-100). Total bupiv volume was calculated.	Total bupiv delivered per hr was ↓ in PIEB grp ($p < .001$), pt satisfaction was ↑ in PIEB grp ($p < .01$), Bromage scale and pain scores were similar among grps.	PIEB resulted in ↓ bupiv admin and ↑ pt satisfaction.
Wong et al. (2006)	DV: need for add'l EPI analg, quality of analg, total bupiv consumption, pt satisfaction.				

Notes: abn = abnormal; add'l = additional; admin = administered; ASA = American Society of Anesthesiologists; analg = analgesia; anes = anesthesia; AMB = automated mandatory bolus; BCI = basal continuous infusion; BMI = body mass index; BTP = breakthrough pain; bupiv = bupivacaine; cath = catheter; cm = centimeter; cerv = cervical; CEI = continuous epidural infusion; C/I = contraindications; ↓ = decreased/less; DV = dependent variable; dil = dilation; d/t = due to; EPI = epidural; EC = exclusion criteria; fent = fentanyl; grp = group; hr = hour; inabil = inability; inadeq = inadequate; incid = incidence; IC = inclusion criteria; ↑ = increased/greater; IDV = independent variable; IEB = intermittent epidural bolus; IT = intrathecal; IV = intravascular; kg = kilogram; LA = local anesthetic; LE = lower extremities; MLAC = mean local anesthetic concentration; mcg = micrograms; mg = milligram; ml = milliliter; min = minute; n/v = nausea/vomiting; OB = obstetric; pt = patient; PCEA = patient-controlled epidural analgesia; PCIA = patient-controlled IV opioid analgesia; preg = pregnancy; prev = previous; PIB = programmed intermittent bolus; PIEB = programmed intermittent epidural bolus; q = every; RCT = randomized control trial; rec = received; req = requesting; resp = respiratory; SE = side effects; sp = spinal; spon = spontaneous; SS = statistically significant; VAPS = visual analog pain score; VRS = verbal rating scale; VAS = visual analog scale; vol = volume; w/ = with; w/o = without.

APPENDIX D

TABLE OF EVIDENCE: EPIDURAL SPACE IDENTIFIER

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
Examine predictors of failed labor EPI and develop a score to help predict risk of inadeq analg. Agaram et al. (2007)	Prospective, OBS study. IDV: LOR tech. DV: inadeq labor analg.	British Columbia Women's Hospital; 275 laboring women with labor EPI over 4 weeks. EC: precipitous delivery, DP, or IV placement.	VPS 1-100, >10 = inadeq analg; pain as back or abdominal pain w/ contractions; < 12ml of LA = low volume & > 12ml LA = high volume; difficult insertion = > 2 attempts or difficult anatomical ID; opioid tolerance = regular use.	Factor SS; LOR w/ air ($p = .04$). Total of 44 women (16.9%) had failed analg; overall prediction rate was 84%.	Wide variation in EPI failures can be in part due to definition of terms; knowledge of RF can change practice of EPI placement and therefore ↓ risk of failed EPI.
To determine the quality of labor analg when using 2 different LOR techs. Beilen et al. (2000).	Prospective, randomized study. IDV: air 2ml or saline 2ml for LOR DV: unacceptable analg, SE, and complications.	Pts in active labor w/ contractions q 5min, req labor EPI; 2 grps: air (n = 80) and saline (n = 80). EC: sp column abnormalities, sp surgery.	VPS (0-10) where 0 = no pain, 10 = worst pain; adeq analg = pt not req add'l meds.	In air grp, 36% req add'l pain meds vs 19% in saline grp ($p = .022$); parasthesias in air vs saline 42% vs 55%, IV caths 5% vs 8% were not SS.	0.9% saline for LOR is assoc w/ improved analg when compared to air; limitations include using 13ml 0.25% bupiv.
A case report of pneumocephalus after LOR with air tech for CLE. Katz et al. (1990)	Case report. IDV: air for LOR. DV: pneumocephalus.	Healthy 25 y/o primip, given EPI for C/S; 16-g tuohy needle, LOR to air approx 20ml injected for confirmation; 16ml 0.5% bupiv w/ epi injected, total sp	None.	Lg SA air-filled cavity in parietofrontal lobe w/ est 25ml volume.	Caution should be used w/ LOR air tech; LOR saline is safer.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
		resulted, intubated, remained intubated post procedure until total sp effects wore off, breathing resumed but pt remained drowsy, CT ordered.			
Examine the effect of a multitude of factors that contribute to inadeq pain relief from labor EPI. Muppuri et al. (2012)	Prospective, OBS study. IDVs: LOR tech using air or saline. DV: Inadeq labor EPI anes.	University Women's Hospital; 502 laboring women req a labor EPI for pain mgmt. EC: rapid progress to 2 nd stage or delivery & pts whose EPI was not in EPI space confirmed by sp tap or IV cannulation; monitored continuously.	Pain = VPS 30min post EPI placement (0-100) with 0 = zero pain & 100 = bad pain; pain = uterine or back pain assoc w/ contractions; VPS > 10 considered inadeq anes.	Predictor SS: air vs saline for LOR ($p = .020$) Best predictors of inadeq epi anes: hx of failed EPI, cerv dil > 7cm, parasthesia, LOR using air.	Pts at high risk may benefit from saline for LOR. Limit: Pts not randomly assigned to LOR tech.
To discuss the incidence of venous air embolism with LOR to air tech in EPI cath insertions. Naulty et al. (1982)	IDV: air for LOR. DV: detectable air embolism.	Brigham & Women's Hospital; 17 healthy first pregnancy women. IC: 18-32 y/o, ASA I, who received labor EPI. EC: OB complications, heart disease, psych issues, toxemia of prenanacy.	Doppler placed over 4 th intercostal space along right sternal border; 5ml saline rapidly injected to confirm placement of Doppler, & deemed correct if change in heart sounds ID; air embolism condition exist if there is opening in vein, and source of air w/ a higher pressure than that in vein.	Air emboli were detected in 43% (8 of 17 pts).	Doppler can detect very small embolism (0.1 ml) but cannot quantify amt of air; all were brief and clinically insig; however EPI anes in pts w/ right to left shunts (venous to arterial circulation could cause air embolus) should use LOR saline.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
To assess the quality of analg when comparing LOR to air or saline in EPI cath. Sanford et al. (2013)	Systematic review. IDV: LOR to air or saline. DV: quality of analg.	Systematic reviews w/ or w/o meta analysis, PubMed, EMBASE, & Cochrane database; Eng language; 4 studies incl $n = 642$. IC: air, fluid, or combination for LOR tech. EC: CSE tech.	Analg quality was primary outcome measured.	LOR tech not SS in terms of qual of analg; LOR air better for determining accidental DP; LOR air assoc w/ more complications such as pneumocephalus.	LOR tech does not affect analg; personal preference and risk of complications should guide decision. Limit: large heterogeneity, small sample sizes, vague definitions and no standard definition regarding analg.
Determine the complications assoc with LOR with air vs LOR with saline. Schier et al. (2009)	Meta-analysis. IDV: LOR w/ air vs saline. DV: EPI related complications.	RCTs from 1966–2008 that compared LOR techniques for ID of EPI space; Ovid, MEDLINE, EMBASE, Cochrane databases searched; Eng language; 5 trials included; $n = 4422$. EC: Peds and animal studies.	Difficult cath insertion, paresthesia, IV cath insertion, DP, PDPH, and partial block were analyzed.	No SS findings among studies for complications; large amount of heterogeneity across studies; low complication rates.	Larger studies are needed to determine the optimal LOR technique.
To determine effectiveness of LOR to saline vs LOR to air. Segal et al. (2010)	Retrospective study. IV: fluid or air as medium for LOR. DV: analg requirements and complications.	929 women at Massachusetts's hospital req labor analg in July/Aug of 2006 & 2007.	Unsatisfactory block = no comfort, one sided, IV cath, wet tap, or cath replacement.	52.6% used LOR air and 47.4% used LOR saline; only SS result was increase in attempts for LOR to air ($p < .002$).	No difference noted between grps in regards to outcomes and complications. More attempts required to find EPI space w/ LOR air.
To determine complications assoc with LOR tech using air and saline.	Systematic review. IDV: LOR to saline or air.	PubMed search from 1966–2002 using key words “EPI anes” and “loss of resistance”	No standard definitions.	Incomplete analg: LOR saline superior in 3 studies ($p < .01$, $p = .022$, $p < .004$); VAE: 3	LOR to saline ↓ morbidity and improves quality of analg.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
Shenouda et al. (2003).	DV: major complications.	IC: Eng language, humans, EPI anes.		studies report this phenomenon w/ air: Pneumo/PDPH: Pneumo only reported w/ air, PDPH more common w/ air in 2 studies ($p < .1, p < .1$); no difference w/ cath paresthesia or nerve root compression; subcutaneous emphysema w/ LOR to air only.	

Notes: add'l = additional; adeq = adequate; ASA = American Society of Anesthesiologists; amt = amount; analg = analgesia; anes = anesthesia; assoc = associated; bupiv = bupivacaine; cath = catheter; cerv = cervical; C/S = cesarean section; CT = computed tomography; CSE = combined spinal/epidural; CLE = continuous lumbar epidural; ↓ = decreased/less; DV = dependent variable; dil = dilation; DP = dural puncture; Eng = English; est = estimated; g = gauge; grp = group; hx = history; EPI = epidural; EC = exclusion criteria; grp = group; ID = identified; inadeq = inadequate; incl = including; IC = inclusion criteria; ↑ = increased/greater; IDV = independent variable; insig = insignificant; IV = intravascular; LA = local anesthetic; LOR = loss of resistance; mgmt. = management; ml = milliliter; min = minute; OBS = observational; OB = obstetric; pt = patient; pneumo = pneumocephalus; PDPH = post dural puncture headache; q = every; qual = quality; RCT = randomized control trial; req = requesting; RF = risk factor; SE = side effect; sp = spinal; SS = statistically significant; SA = subarachnoid; tech = technique; VAE = venous air embolism; VPS = verbal pain scale; vs = versus; w/ = with; w/o = without; y/o = year old.

APPENDIX E

TABLE OF EVIDENCE: MULTIPORT/UNIPOINT CATHETERS

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
Evaluate the risks and benefits of multiport and single port EPI cath on patient analg. D' Angelo et al. (1997)	RCT. IDV: multiport or single port cath. DV: insertion related complications.	500 ASA I and II women req EPI w/o C/I.	Sensory levels to pinprick, IV cannulation, inadeq analg, cath manipulation, cath dislodgement, cath replacement.	Multiport cath resulted in ↓ amount of inadeq analg (21.2% vs 31.8%) and # of cath manipulations (31.4% vs 44.2%, $p < .05$). No other results SS.	Multiport cath ↓ inadeq analg and cath manipulation and should be used exclusively.
To evaluate the efficacy of multiport cath. Fegley et al. (2008)	In vitro study. IDV: flow rates and boluses. DV: use of selected multiport cath orifices.	4 multiport cath from 2 distributors; all had 3 orifices	Flow rates shown in ml/hr, boluses shown in ml/s.	1 orifice = infusion rate <80 ml/hr, 2 orifices = infusion rate 100 – 280 ml/hr and three orifices = infusion rate > 300ml/hr; boluses ranged from 0.2 – 0.4 ml/sec.	Multiport cath act like single port cath w/ infusion pumps, but act like multiport cath when manual boluses are admin.
Evaluate the effect of a single port cath on EPI vein cannulation. Mhyre et al. (2009)	Systematic review IDV: Single vs multiport cath. DV: IV EPI cannulation.	Medline, EMBASE, Cochrane, & CINAHL databases searched, 5 RCTs included; Eng language between 1984-2007, n = 2227.	Multiport cath threaded deeper, was not listed as primary outcome in any study.	EPI vein cannulation rate was lower in single orifice cath than multiport cath (10% vs 6.8%).	Single port cath ↓ the risk of EPI vein cannulation; the definition for IV cannulation was widely varied.
To determine efficacy and complication rate between multiport and single port EPI cath. Michael et al. (1989)	Randomized, single-blind study. IDV: single port vs multiport cath.	802 women req EPI anes; 2 groups: 402 received single hole, 402 received multiport.	Inadeq analg = 1 sided, missed segments, or incomplete analg.	27 EPIs were inadeq in single hole vs 4 in multiport ($p < .001$); no SS findings re: complications; SS findings in sensory	Multiport cath produce better qual of analg w/ no ↑ in complication rates.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
	DV: complications and qual of analg.	IC: 16-40 years, ASA I-II, no current meds.		blockade: 55 in multiport vs 131 in single hole were inadeq analg ($p < .001$).	
Determine if there is an advantage in using single orifice or multiport catheters for labor analg and cesarean delivery. Segal et al. (1997).	Prospective, cohort study. IDV: multiport or single port cath. DV: inadeq analg requiring replacement.	433 single port pts and 439 multiport pts.	Incidence of parasthesias, inadeq block, pt satisfaction, wet tap, replacement or reposition of cath.	Replacement rate 14.3% vs 9.3% (multiport); SS fewer multiport cath replaced (6.4% vs 2.8%, $p = .018$). Parasthesias less frequent in multiport grp (22.4% vs 31.5%, $p = .003$).	Multiport catheters offer significant advantages over single orifice catheters.

Notes: admin = administered; analg = analgesia; anes = anesthesia; ASA = American Society of Anesthesiologists; cath = catheter; C/I = contraindication; ↓ = decreased/less; DV = dependent variable; Eng = English; EPI = epidural; grp = group; hr = hour; inadeq = inadequate; IC = inclusion criteria; ↑ = increased/greater; IDV = independent variable; IV = intravascular; med = medication; ml = milliliters; qual = quality; pt = patient; RCT = randomized control trial; req = requesting; sec = second; SS = statistically significant; vs = versus; w/ = with; w/o = without.

APPENDIX F

TABLE OF EVIDENCE: PATIENT POSITIONING

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
Determine the optimal position of a laboring patient for EPI placement. Bahar et al. (2004)	RCT. IDV: pt position for EPI placement. DV: vessel cannulation.	450 morbidly obese laboring pts assigned to 1 of 3 grps in sitting, lat recumbent, & lat recumbent head down position.	Primary outcome: blood in EPI cath; related variables: blood on needle puncture, SA puncture, > 1 attempt.	IV EPI cath significantly ↓ in lat head down pt (1.3%) compared to sitting pt (12.0%, $p < .001$). Blood in cath and needle were also ↓ in lat head down position compared to sitting position though not SS.	EPI cath placement in the lateral position ↓ venous congestion in the EPI veins and therefore ↓ vein cannulation. Limit: Can only be generalized to morbidly obese pts.
To determine EPI cath movement based on pt positioning. Hamilton et al. (1997)	IDV: sitting flexed, sitting upright, lat decub position. DV: position of EPI cath.	225 women req EPI anes for labor or C/S; 3 grps BMI < 25, BMI 25-39, BMI > 40.	Cath movement w/ position change.	Cath movement was greatest in BMI>40 grp.	Position of EPI caths can vary greatly w/ pt position changes & are most significant in obese pts. Taping EPI cath in lat position yielded highest success.
Evaluate effect of pt positioning on EPI vein cannulation. Mhyre et al. (2009)	Systematic review. IDV: pt positioning during EPI placement. DV: IV EPI cannulation.	Medline, EMBASE, Cochrane, & CINAHL databases searched, 6 RCTs included; Eng language between 1984-2007, n = 1403.	2 RCTs included lat head down position, 2 included CSE, and in 3 trials IV cath placement was primary outcome.	Placement of EPI cath w/ pt in lateral position vs sitting ↓ EPI vein cannulation (11.9% vs 6.7%).	Placing the pt in the lat position for EPI placement ↓ IV cannulation; the definition for IV cannulation was widely varied.

Notes: anes = anesthesia; BMI = body mass index; cath = catheter; C/S = cesarean section; CSE = combined spinal/epidural; ↓ = decreased/less; decub = decubitus; DV = dependent variable; Eng = English; EPI = epidural; grp = group; incl = including; ↑ = increased/greater; IDV = independent variable; IV = intravascular; lat = lateral; pt = patient; RCT = randomized controlled trial; req = requesting; sig = significant; SA = subarachnoid; SS = statistically significant; vs = versus; w/ = with.

APPENDIX G

TABLE OF EVIDENCE: SALINE PRE-DISTENTION OF EPIDURAL SPACE

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
Determine the effect of predistention on IV EPI cath insertion. Evron et al. (2007)	RCT. IDV: 2ml or 5ml saline distention. DV: IV EPI cath placement.	210 ASA I-II first baby w/ one fetus head down req an EPI. EC: preeclampsia, morbid obesity, hx substance abuse, heavy smoker, abn liver, kidney, or blood results, C/S delivery.	Sensory block measured by VAS pain score, Bromage scale used to assess motor block (0-3), and total dose of ropiv calculated. IV or SA puncture also recorded by MDA placing EPI.	Onset of analg faster in distention grp ($p < .001$), fewer accidental IV caths (2 vs 16, $p = .0001$), 91% had 0 missing areas as compared to 67% in which saline was not used grp ($p = .0001$).	Predistention w/ 5ml NS into EPI space prior to cath placement ↓ IV cath placement, ↓ patchy blocks, and ↓ time to comfort therefore ↓ complications and improving EPI tech.
Determine if predistention of EPI space ↓ IV puncture rates. Gadalla et al. (2003)	Prospective, RCT. IDV: 10ml saline predistension. DV: IV EPI cath placement.	100 women req CSE labor analg carrying vertex, singleton fetuses; placed by experienced providers.	IV cath placement confirmed by free flowing blood in EPI cath or by positive epinephrine test dose.	IV cath placement was ↑ in dry grp vs fluid predistention grp (2% vs 20%, $p < .01$).	Injecting 10ml of saline immediately before EPI cath insertion ↓ the risk of EPI vein cannulation from 20% to 2%.
To determine the effect of preloading the EPI space on pt complications. Geng et al. (2013)	RCT. IDV: 5 ml of NS preloading vs no preloading. DV: IV injection and parasthesia.	290 laboring pts at Fudan University Hospital; 2 grps: control (grp 1) and NS (grp II). IC: full term, 21-45 y/o, ASA I-II, 60-90kg weight, having C/S under CSE anes. EC: sp deform & C/I to sp anes.	Parasthesia during cath placement (grade 0-2, grade 0 = no pain, grade 1 = some pain, grade 2 = sig pain or involuntary mvmt of legs; IV injection confirmed by red fluid in cath was recorded.	IV injury in grp 1 and 2 was 23 and 3 respectively ($p < .01$); no change in # of parasthesias.	Incidence of IV injury ↓ significantly with 5 ml NS preloading prior to EPI cath insertion.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
To determine the changes in the anatomy of the EPI space in pregnant pts. Igarashi et al. (2000)	OBS study. DV: Epiduroscopy in non-pregnant, 1 st trimester, & 3 rd trimester pregnancy. IDV: changes in EPI space.	73 pts undergoing EPI anes; 3 groups: nonpregnant ($n = 21$), 8 – 13 weeks gest ($n = 23$), & 27–39 weeks ($n = 29$). EC: hx of prior EPI anes, neuro disease, sp deform, coagulopathy.	Size of space w/ air (1 – 3 scale; 1 = very narrow, 2 = patent, 3 = widely patent; density of vasc network, amt of engorged BV, water in conn tissue, degree of bleeding at needle site, amt of fatty tissue, amt of conn tissue (1 – 3 scale, 1 = none or little, 2 = mod, 3 = considerable).	Pneumatic space after air injection was ↓ ($p = .0347$) and vasc congestion was ↑ ($p = .0001$) in 3 rd trimester grps compared to other 2 grps; engorged BV ↑ in 1 st and 3 rd trimester preg than in non-pregnant pts.	EPI vessels are engorged in 1 st trimester and vasc congestion increases in 3 rd trimester putting pt at ↑ risk for IV cannulation.
Evaluate effect of fluid predistention on EPI vein cannulation. Mhyre et al. (2009)	Systematic review. DV: fluid predistention. IDV: IV EPI cannulation.	Medline, EMBASE, Cochrane, & CINAHL databases searched, 8 RCTs included; Eng language between 1984-2007, $n = 1427$.	2 studies compared LOR techniques, 5 studies used standard LOR, and 1 study evaluated both. In 4 studies, IV cath placement was primary outcome.	Fluid predistention ↓ the IV cannulation rate from 12.9% to 6.4%.	IV cannulation is ↓ with fluid predistention; the definition for IV cannulation was widely varied.
To determine techniques that reduces the risk of IV cannulation with EPI cath. Shih et al. (2012)	Retrospective review. DV: soft tip & stiff EPI cath. IDV: incid of IV injection.	1124 laboring pts at Kaohsiung Medical University Hospital; 2 grps. IC: ASA I-III, req labor analg. EC: morbid obesity, prev sp surgery, C/I to EPI.	IV cannulation: heme in cath flowing cont w/ aspiration.	Incidence of IV cannulation lower in soft tip grp (1.5% vs 4.6%) ($p = .003$).	Soft tip EPI cath ↓ IV cannulation; they also ↓ DP, LBP, and EPI failure rate although not SS.

Notes: abn = abnormal; amt = amount; analg = analgesia; ASA = American Society of Anesthesiologists; anes = anesthesia; BV = blood vessel; cath = catheter; C/S = cesarean section; CSE = combined spinal/epidural; conn = connective; cont = continuous; C/I = contraindication; ↓ = decreased/less; DV = dependent variable; DP = dural puncture; EPI = epidural; EC = exclusion criteria; gest = gestation; grp = group; hx = history; IC = inclusion criteria; ↑ = increased/greater; IDV = independent variable; IV = intravascular; LOR = loss of resistance; LBP = low back pain; MDA = medical doctor of anesthesiology; mvmt = movement; NS = normal saline; OBS = observational; pt = patient; prev = previous; RCT = randomized control trial; req = requesting; ropiv = ropivacaine; sig = significant; sp = spinal; SS = statistically significant; SA = subarachnoid; vasc = vascular; vs = versus; VAS = visual analog scale; w/ = with; y/o = year old.

APPENDIX H

TABLE OF EVIDENCE: PREDICTORS OF FAILED LABOR ANALGESIA

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
To determine factors assoc with inadeq labor EPI analg. Agaram et al. (2007)	Prospective, OBS study. DV: 4 pt characteristics, 5 labor details, & 7 EPI techs. IDV: inadeq labor analg.	British Columbia Women's Hospital; 275 laboring women with labor EPI over 4 weeks; EC: precipitous delivery, DP, or IV placement; tech and meds chosen by provider; sitting or lateral position, 18 g EPI cath, single port, 5-40 ml of LA; bupiv w/ or w/o addition of fent.	VPS 1-100, > 10 = inadeq analg; pain as back or abd pain w/ contractions; < 12 ml of LA = low volume & > 12 ml LA = high volume; diff insertion = > 2 attempts or diff anatomical ID; opioid tolerance = regular use.	Multiparity ($p = .028$), hx of failed EPI ($p = .009$), LOR w/ air ($p = .035$), & cerv dil > 7cm ($p = .016$) are assoc w/ inadeq labor analg.	Early placement of EPI and LOR w/ saline may improve EPI labor analg.
Evaluate 7 RF assoc with inabil to use EPI for C/S deliveries. Bauer et al. (2012)	Systematic review and meta-analysis search of databases: 13 articles. IDV: CSE, duration of EPI, cervical dilation when EPI placed, BMI, # boluses required, ↑ urgency for C/S, & non-OB anes. DV: Failed use of labor EPI analgesia for C/S.	Electronic databases of OBS studies in Eng published from 1979-2011. IC: OBS study with failed conversion in the title. EC: non-Eng, case reports, studies, meta-analysis, or reference to IT, GA, PP mgmt, or neonatal outcomes.	Meta-analysis included data from articles discussing conversion of EPI anes or failure rates w/o assoc RF; Point estimate and 95% CI were obtained. STROBE statement assessed the investigator in their evaluations.	CSE, duration of EPI, cervical dilation when EPI placed, & BMI: not SS, no difference; ↑ boluses was SS.	Failed use of labor EPI for C/S deliveries with ↑ top offs, ↑ urgency of C/S; Further studies needed.
Determine risks for DEP and develop an estimation score.	Prospective cross-sectional study.	Bichat Hospital OB ward in Paris, France; 2 randomized grps:	Palp of IS space: good, poor, or nil; diff for poor or nil; BMI:	3 RF ID for DEP incl diff palp of IS space, spine deformity, &	RFs for DEP were confirmed & allow for interventions such as

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
Guglielminotti et al. (2013)	IDV: palp of IS space, obesity, sp deformity, ability to flex sp, provider level of experience. DV: diff of EPI placement.	training grp (N = 165) and validation grp (N = 165); received EPI in sitting position; LOR w/ saline, skin anes w/ 2% lido, 18 g tuohy via ML approach, choice of L3-L4 or L4-L5 space, resident could not perform > 2 punctures. IC: laboring pts req lumbar EPI. EC: C/I to EPI, refusal, or hx or sp surgery.	continous variable; sp deformity = deviation from ML or unable to palpate sp process; Inabil. to flex spine: convex, straight, or concave where straight or concave = inabil to flex; provider level of experience: proficient = > 100 EPI placed. DEP = > 1 skin puncture w/ tuohy EPI placement.	inabil to flex the back; all were SS ($p < .05$). DP was \uparrow in pts. w/ DEP (4 of 98) vs. w/o DEP (0 of 232). Diff palpation of IS space was assoc with highest risk as OR was 2x that of sp deformity and inabil to flex back; The CI in training grp was 0.81 & in validation grp was 0.79.	US to facilitate placement of EPI cath.; Limits: no blinding of anes personnel placing the EPI.
To determine RF for accidental DP when placing labor EPIs. Hollister et al. (2012)	Retrospective review. DV: LOR tech, pt position, cerv dil, EPI depth, and time of insertion. IDV: DP.	18,385 EPI placed from Jan 1992 – Dec 2006 at Derriford Hospital.	DP = CSF return in needle, cath, or positive test dose.	129 DPs were found = 1/143 EPI placed; incidence rate 0.70%.	Risk of DP \uparrow with \uparrow depth to EPI space. Limits: retrospective and 1 site; lots of missing data on LOR tech and pt. position.
To examine various factors that contribute to inadeq analg w/ labor EPIs. Muppuri et al. (2012)	Prospective, OBS study. DV: 5 pt characteristics, 6 labor details, 6 EPI techs, & time of insertion. IDV: inadeq pain relief.	University Women's Hospital; 502 laboring women req a labor EPI for pain mgmt. EC: rapid progress to 2 nd stage or delivery & pts whose EPI was not in EPI space confirmed by sp tap or IV	Diff EPI placement = > 2 attempts or diff ID landmarks; inadeq analg = VPS 10 w/ contractions 30 min post placement or need of add'l LA w/in 30 min of placement.	Cerv dil > 7cm ($p = .001$), hx failed EPI ($p = .001$), + parasthesia ($p = .001$), & LOR to air ($p = .020$) were best predictors of inadeq labor analg.	Use of US guided, saline for LOR, & appropriate cath length should be adopted in pts w/ RF for failed analg.

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
		cannulation; monitored continuously.			
To determine the incidence and types of failures in OB anes & analg. Pan et al. (2004)	Through an ongoing QA program, a retrospective analysis of 3-year database of OB anes & analg outcomes; data collected between Jan 2000 – Dec 2002. QA processes: QA form for each pt filled out by provider consisting of complications, failures, and descriptions; a post-anes; 1 dedicated QA MDA to review records daily and ID problems.	19,259 deliveries; 24-hr single OB anes faculty overlooking trainees; 17 g tuohy, 18 g multiport EPI cath; inserted 5-6 cm in EPI space, 2-5 ml lido 2% used to test placement; 0.11% bupiv w/ or w/o fent admin via PCEA with base rate 6-12 ml/hr.	Failure = inadeq analg or lack of sensory block, sp tap, IV placement, needing replacement, or requiring add'l mgmt. EPI failures for C/S = inadeq analg requiring replacement or conversion to different type of anesthetic; ANOVA analyzed interval data and χ^2 and Fisher's exact test analyzed nominal data. $P < .05$ was SS.	All results were SS; overall EPI failure rate was 14%; For initial placement 7% went IV and 1.4% were known wet tap. Inadeq analg was present in 8.4% of pts, 7.1% needed replacement, and 1.4% needed multiple replacements; for C/S usage 7.1% EPI cath failed: 1.3% were replaced, 1.5% converted to SAB, and 4.3% converted to GA.	Limitations include a huge sample size for a prospective study; non-controlled; bias can be present when selecting and reporting; risk of not reporting; future studies needed.
Determine the incidence of inadeq anes for C/S using previously placed labor EPI. Riley et al. (2001)	Retrospective chart review of anesthetic records. IDV: urgency of C/S, \uparrow labor EPI, maternal BMI. DV: success rate of EPI cath for C/S.	246 pts from May 1, 1997 – May 1, 1998 with EPI cath requiring C/S for delivery; EPI placed by residents or attending MDA; standard tech with 12–15 ml 0.125% bupiv. w/ sufenta followed by base rate 12–15 ml/hr; 2-8 cm inside EPI space; for C/S 2% lido. w/ EPI & bicarb.	OB specialist – part of the main grp of MDAs who specialize in OB anes & provide most of day coverage; non-specialist – cover OB at night or on weekends; χ^2 , t-test, and U test.	2 main factors contributed to failure of EPI cath for surgical anes: # of extra boluses needed for comfort & specialty of the provider; most significant was # of boluses; overall failure rate was 8%.	If \uparrow # of boluses are required to maintain pt. comfort, consider replacing the cath. OB anes specialists may feel more confident than non-specialists and less likely to convert method.
Determine if US-guided EPI placement \downarrow	Prospective, RCT.	Magee-Womens Hospital; 370 laboring pts into 2 randomized	EPI attempt – advancing the needle in an attempt to get into	US grp had \downarrow # of EPI cath replacements ($p < .02$) & attempts at	US-guided EPI placement can be used to facilitate the anes

Purpose, Source	Design, Key Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures	Findings	Authors Conclusions; Limitations
replacement rate of EPI cath. To correlate US estimated depth with actual needle depth in EPI placement. Vallejo et al. (2010)	IDV: US measurement of EPI depth. DV: EPI cath replacement incidence, # attempts, # DPs.	grps; US grp ($n = 189$): EPI depth determined by US prior to being sat up & control grp ($n = 181$): no use of US before sitting; IC: req labor EPI. EC: coagulopathy, prior sp surgery, LA allergy; US visualization in 3 planes by trained primary investigator; EPI placed by 15 trained residents.	EPI space; removal to redirect or reinsert counted as add'l attempts; > 6 attempts required intervening; failed EPI – needing replacement during labor; early failure < 90 mins, late failure > 90 mins; pain measured on VAS scale 1-10; score > 3 = failed EPI; personal and OB data collected; actual needle depth to EPI space also recorded.	placement ($p < .01$); US estimated EPI depth was highly accurate to true depth of EPI space (Pearson's corr coefficient 0.914 and 0.909).	providers abil to determine ML, needle angle, and depth to EPI space resulting in ↓ failures, attempts, and ↑ pt. satisfaction; limitations include no blinding of researcher or participant, and no randomization of provider.
Determine the effect of repeat EPI on unilateral blocks. Withington et al. (1994).	Prospective study. IDV: 1 st vs 2 nd EPI. DV: performance and outcome.	221 laboring patients (150 first pregnancy/ 71 second or more pregnancy) req EPI analg giving informed consent. EC: language barrier, obvious reason for diff EPI placement (scoliosis).	VAS measured before EPI and 30 min after placement; level of sensory blockade tested to cold; unilateral block = worse pain on one side, pain only on one side, not resolved with bolus medication.	Unilateral block was more common in multigravida (18.3%) vs first pregnancy (6.7%) ($p < .02$).	Having multiple EPIs placed ↑ the pts risk for 1-sided or unilateral block.

Notes: abd = abdominal; abil = ability; admin = administered; analg = analgesia; ANOVA = analysis of variance; anes = anesthesia; assoc = associated; bicarb = bicarbonate; BMI = body mass index; bupiv = bupivacaine; CSF = cerebrospinal fluid; cerv = cervical; C/S = cesarean section; CES = combined spinal/epidural; CI = confidence interval; C/I = contraindication; corr = correlation; ↓ = decreased/less; DV = dependent variable; diff = difficult; DEP = difficult epidural predictors; dil = dilation; DP = dural puncture; Eng = English; EPI = epidural; fent = fentanyl; g = gauge; GA = general anesthesia; grp = group; hx = history; ID = identified; inabil = inability; inadeq = inadequate; incl = including; IC = inclusion criteria; ↑ = increased/greater; IDV = independent variable; IS = interspinous; IT = intrathecal; IV = intravenous; lido = lidocaine; LA = local anesthetic; LOR = loss of resistance; L3 = lumbar 3; L4 = lumbar 4; L5 = lumbar 5; mgmt = management; MDA = medical doctor of anesthesiology; meds = medications; ML = midline; OBS = observational; OB = obstetric; OR = odds ratio; pt =

patient; pp = post partum; PCEA = programmed continuous epidural anesthesia; QA = quality assurance; RCT = randomized control trial; req = requesting; RF = risk factors; sp = spinal; SS = statistically significant; STROBE = Strengthening the Reporting in Observational Studies and Epidemiology; SAB = subarachnoid block; syst = systematic; US = ultrasound; vs = versus; VAS = visual analog scale; VPS = verbal pain scale; w/ = with; w/o = without; χ^2 = chi square.